

The Mughal Inroads in Tripura: An Overview

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This paper attempts to explore the historical perspective of the Mughal inroads in Tripura. Actually, in 1240 C.E., Tripura was first attacked by Hiravanta Khan and since 1240 C.E, Tripura was several times attacked from the west by the Pathans and the Mughals. This paper highlights the political condition of Tripura before the Mughal inroads in the light of the administrative policies of its rulers as well as the social conditions of this tiny state. The impact of the Muslim invasion in Tripura finds an important place in this paper. As a whole, this paper makes an attempt to study the Mughal inroads in Tripura so as to understand their Socio-cultural and historical impact.

Introduction

The early history of Tripura, particularly prior to the 15th century, is shrouded in the mists of legend and tradition. According to Dr. Suniti Kumar Chatterjee, "The historical account of Tripura begins from the 15th century, when king Dharma Manikya...."¹ The history relating to the period prior to the 15th century has been written on the basis of traditions (recorded and unrecorded) as well as imagination.² Even Pandit Kaliprasanna Sen, author of *Rajmala*, admits his difficulty in utilizing the epigraphic material available to him, presumably because he could not reconcile the evidence of inscriptions with the details supplied by the *Rajmala*.....There are cases where the author is silent about the expert opinion.³ The state's history, therefore, relates to two distinct periods- the traditional period as recorded in the *Rajmala* (chronicles of the Tripura Rajas) and the historical period recorded in the writings of the Mohammedan historians as well as in *Rajmala*.⁴

The origin and history of the Tripura Raj is given in the *Rajmala* (literary meaning the Garland of Kings) or chronicles of Tripura. It is the oldest specimen of Bengali composition extant. It is in verse and was in a detached form, but was collected and written in sequence by the Brahmin officials of Raja Dharma

Manikya, the 102nd Raja, who ascended the throne of the Tripura kingdom in 1407 C.E. His Successors continued the task year by the year until we have now one of the oldest, continuous chronicles of any Indian reigning family. We also come across some valuable Muslim accounts and some historical literature including, 'Ghazi Nama',⁵ Chanpakvijoy,⁶ Tripura Desar Kathar Lekha⁷ & Krishnamala,⁸ which are interesting and meaningful. Besides these, we have a considerable number of coins issued by the rulers and several inscriptions on the walls of some temples which are of much help in reconstructing the history of the relevant period.

Condition of Tripura before the Mughal Inroads

Originally the rulers of Tripura had not assumed the title 'Manikya' but were known by the surname 'Fa' meaning father. The Tripura rajas are said to have assumed the title manikya from the time of Ratna Pha⁹ who, according to professor Kalikaranjan Qanungo, was a contemporary of Sultan Ghiyasuddin Balban¹⁰ Ratna Fa was defeated by Sultan Mughisuddin Tughril in about 1280 C.E. and upon his submission was honoured by the Muslim ruler with the title 'Manikya'. He was also helped to regain his territory, and as a mark of respect as well as in the recognition of the services rendered by the Sultan of Gour; the latter was presented with precious stones and some elephants. He is said to have invited many Bengalees to settle in Tripura.¹¹ Among the new settlers, there were many who were related to Baro-Bhuyia, the twelve zamindars of Bengal. It was mainly through his patronage that Hinduism started yielding a considerable influence in this predominant tribal area. Ratna Pha is believed to have introduced certain administrative reforms on the "Bengalee Pattern." This must have led to closer ties in religion and culture between the Indo-Mongloid people of the state and the Bengalees. However, opinions differ not only about the period during which Ratna Pha ruled in Tripura, but also on the point whether he was the first ruler to use the title 'Manikya.' It is therefore difficult to ascertain as to who was the actual founder of the ruling dynasty. However, the differences of opinion and doubts among the historians about the actual founder of the ruling dynasty notwithstanding,¹² one may maintain that the Tripura ruling dynasty was at the zenith of its power and glory during the 15th and 16th centuries C.E. This period was mainly marked by the reigns of

four rulers, namely, Dharma Manikya(1431-1462 C.E), Dhanya Manikya (C.1490-1515C.E.), Vijay Manikya (C.1529-1564C.E)and Amar Manikya (C.1577-1586C.E.)¹³

During the reign of Pratap Manikya, son of Ratna Manikya, the capital of Bengal was transferred to Subarnagram. This brought the Mohammedans into closer touch with Tripura and in 1347 C.E., Samsuddin, the Pathan Sultan, invaded Tripura and took away some elephants and money as booty. Muslim historians have with pride mentioned this as a conquest of Tripura, but it seems to be an exaggeration pure and simple.¹⁴ It is said that the most noteworthy event of the reign of Dharma Manikya (C.1431-1462C.E) was his invasion of Bengal under Sultan Abul Mujahed Ahmed Shah and the plunder of Subarnagram, the capital of the Nawab.¹⁵ About this time, Mengchu Muang, the ruler of Arakan, was dethroned by the king of Burma and took refuge at the court of Tripura. Dharma Manikya helped him with both men and money and got him reinstated.¹⁶ The reign of Dharma Manikya was characterized by all-around peace and prosperity. The well-known tank, Dharma Sagar of Comilla, was excavated by him, while 'Nanuar Dighi', another well-known tank of that city was excavated as the name suggests by his queen Nanua.

Dharma Manikya had two sons – Dhanya and Pratap. Dharma's death was followed by a scramble for the throne. As usual, commanders of the Army took a leading part in this affair. By a conspiracy Dhanya was made king, but he was soon put to death. With a view to save the life of Dhanya, his nurse kept him hidden in the house of the Raj priest. Coming to know of this, the Commander-in-chief found him out and put him on the throne in 1490C.E. and gave his daughter Kamala in marriage to him.

Historical Perspective of Mughal Inroads in Tripura

With a view to consolidate his power and place his throne on a firmer footing, Dhanya Manikya recognized the army and introduced many reforms. The old Generals who aspired to, and practically did for sometime control the affairs of Government were removed and put to death. New posts of different grades were created and filled up by able officers. After re-organizing his army, Dhanya turned his attention towards the conquest of Bengal, and within a short time conquered Meherkul, Patikara, Ganga Mondal, Bagasair, Bejura, Bhanugach, Bishnajuri, Longla,

Bardakhat etc. But, the ruler of Khandal did not accept the subjugation of Tripura. He captured the Governor of Tripura and sent him as a captive to the king of Gour, who got him trampled to death by an elephant. This naturally enraged Dhanya Manikya, who sent his commander Roy Kachag to Khandal. By clever diplomacy, Roy Kachag brought the 12 land holders of Khandal before Dhanya Manikya and got them assassinated. Khandal then came under the subjugation of Tripura.¹⁷

Arguably, the greatest king, Dhanya Manikya made his mark in Tripura's history as conqueror and judicious ruler and crowned himself with the titles of 'Tripurendra' and 'Vijayendra'. The war of Dhanya Manikya with Hussain Shah, Nawab of Gour, for supremacy over Chittagong, is a important historical event. It was a long and terrible war. It was during his rule that Hussain Shah (C.1493-1519C.E), the Nawab of Bengal invaded Tripura thrice in the years 1512,1513 and 1514, but on all occasions heavy defeats were inflicted on the attacking armies by king Dhanya Manikya and his competent generals Ray Kachag and Ray Kacham.¹⁸ The king of Tripura drove out the army of the Nawab from Chittagong and took possession of his territory. At this Hussain Shah sent a vast army under his General Gour Mallik, which met the Tripura forces and Tripura forces were routed out, but in the second, they met with a decisive victory. Most of the Nawab's soldiers met with watery graves in the violent current of the Gumti. The tank, popularly called 'Dhanyer Dighi' within the memorial tower on its bank still stands as a living witness to the great success achieved by King Dhanya. But, the Nawab of Gour was not the man to bear the insult lying down. He sent another big army under Haiton Khan. Haiton attained some success and occupied a few forts of Tripura, but his soldiers were ultimately routed and drowned in the river.

Dhanya Manikya commemorated this victory over the Nawab by building in 1501 C.E. the famous temple of Tripura Sundari at Udaipur. The big tank of Kamalasagar which still exists as a standing monument of the constructive genius of king Dhanya was excavated and named after his queen Kamala Devi.¹⁹

After the death of Dhanya Manikya, Dhwaja Manikya followed him to the throne, but died soon after. So, the brother of Dhanya Manikya named as Deva Manikya, the next important king, ascended to the throne in 1520 C.E. and conquered the

Parganah of Bhuluya and compelled its king to pay him revenue annually. But fresh quarrels broke out with the Nawab of Gour. The old question of the possession of Chittagong got renewed again and Hussain Shah's son Nasarath Shah succeeded in ousting the soldiers of Tripura from Chittagong and in establishing his power there. But Deva Manikya's son, Bijoy Manikya was more powerful than his father. He conquered Sylhet, Khasia and Joyantia hills and drove away the Mussalmans from Chittagong in a terrible battle, in which his great General Kala Nazir was killed, but the Pathan general Momarak Khan, brother-in-law of the king of Gour, was captured. The captive was sent to the king of Tripura and was sacrificed before the image of 14 Gods. Bijoy Manikya was a contemporary of Emperor Akbar and ruled from 1528 to 1570 C.E. with much credit having accomplished many goods deeds for the benefit of his people.²⁰

Rangamati (the present Udaipur in South Tripura) was annexed by Jujarpha, the 74th Raja of Tripura from the Raja of Lika, who opposed the move and led a disciplined army of 10 thousand men. Rangamati was then made the capital of the kingdom. Long afterwards the name was changed to Udaipur, perhaps by Raja Udai Manikya in whose reign the King of Gour again invaded Chittagong and occupied some parts of the possessions of Tripura. After Udai Manikya's death, his son Joy Manikya became king, who was a mere puppet in the hands of his General Rangan Narain. Rangan was, however put to death by Amar, son of Deva Manikya. Amar, in his turn, killed Joy Manikya and ascended the throne. He defeated and brought under control the rebellious Zamidars of Taraf in Sylhet and compelled the insubordinate Raja of Bhuluya to pay him regular revenue and also conquered Bakla Chandradwip, which was then growing into a flourishing place. Immediately after these events Islam Khan, Nawab of Dacca shifted his capital to Dacca and attacked the kingdom of Tripura. But his army sustained a heavy defeat at the hands of Ishakhan, the commander of Amar Manikya.

Emboldened by these victories Amar Manikya led an expedition to Arakhan and occupied a few places. In retaliation, the ruler of Arakan sought the help of the Portuguese and with their aid not only snatched off Chittagong, but attacked Udaipur, ransacked the capital and carried a large booty. Amar Manikya saved his life by a timely flight, but he was too proud a king to endure

such an ignominy and put an end to his life by poisoning. King Amar gave away innumerable taluks as free gifts to Brahmins and deities to which many more were added by his son Rajdhar Manikya, who ruled for 3 years and kept himself away from the battle field and devoted himself to religious pursuits. His indifference to the affairs of the state induced the Nawab of Bengal to attack Tripura, but he had to beat a hasty retreat.

It was during the rule of Jehangir that the Tripura state suffered most. In the year 1618 C.E., when Jasodhar Manikya, the son of Rajdhar Manikya was the king, Tripura was subjugated by Mughals after a brief siege of the capital Udaipur. The capital was sacked and the state remained under Mughal rule during 1618-20C.E, when people in general were looted. Prohibition was imposed on tradition worship of deities in religious places including 'Tripureswari temple.'²¹

King Jasodhar Manikya was succeeded by his son Kalyan Manikya, who was a good ruler and was able to regain to some extent the lost glory of the country. He re-organised the army and excavated the well-known tank called Kalyansagar and founded the Kali temple at Kashba. After his death, a feud broke out between his sons Govinda and Nakshatra for the crown. Govinda, the elder, unexpectedly brought all troubles to an end by withdrawing in favour of his younger brother.

Thus, Nakshatra Roy ascended the throne under the name of Chhatra Manikya. During his reign Tavernier, the French traveller, came out to India. In his travelogue (P-156), it is stated that the east of the Mughal empire there were 3 independent states, viz, Assam, Tripura and Arakan. This shows the independent status of Tripura.

Nakshatra Ray was a contemporary of Shah Jahan, the famous Mughal emperor. After Aurangzeb's accession to the throne of Delhi, his second brother Suja with his Begum Peri Banu took shelter in Tripura and passed sometime at the hermitage of Govinda Manikya on their way to Arakan. Emperor Aurangzeb wrote a friendly letter to Chhatra Manikya recognizing his independence and requesting him to send his brother and sister-in-law as captives to him, but Chhatra Manikya refused to bring a slur on the noble traditions of his family by ascending to such an unwarranted request of the Emperor ²².

After the death of Chhatra Manikya, his elder brother Govinda Manikya became an ideal king loved and respected by the high and the low alike. The Gumti embankment and the famous temple of Chandranath were built by him. His chief fame lies in the construction of the noted Suja Mosque of Comilla, which he built as a mark of friendship between himself and the unfortunate Suja with whom he had an opportunity of passing sometime in the forest while in exile. How great, good and tolerant he was, is evidenced by the fact that he is the Central figure of the novel 'Rajarshi' (The Saint King) and the famous drama 'Bisarjan' (Immersion) of poet Rabindranath Tagore.²³

After Govinda Manikya, the throne of Tripura was occupied in succession by Ramdeb Manikya, Narendra Manikya and Ratna Manikya II, Ratna Manikya was put to death by his brother Mahendra Manikya. After the death of Mahendra Manikya, Dharma Manikya II, ascended to the throne in 1714 CE, in whose reign the Kingdom of Tripura fell from its position of glory and Jagat Roy, a descendant of King Chhatra Manikya, rebelled against the throne and with the help of the Nayeb Nazim of Dacca, attacked Tripura. The King in utter helplessness at this unexpected attack, fled to the hills and Jagat Roy was declared King of the plains which was named Roshanabad or the 'Land of Light' by the victorious Mahomedans. Dharma Manikya II in despair appealed to Nawab Suzauddin of Murshidabad, who granted him the Zamindari right of the Parganah of Roshnabad on a yearly rent of Rs. 500/- since then the Kings of Tripura have been in possession of Roshanabad as Zamindars.

The Impact of Mughal Inroads in Tripura

The impact of the Mughal inroads can be summed up as follows:-

Tripura as an Independent Kingdom

European historians have referred to the development in the following words :-

"The Province of Tippera, which from time immemorial had been an independent kingdom, became annexed to the Mughal empire."²⁴

But one's view of the matter is that this did not mean the loss of independent status as far as the Hill Territory of Tripura

is concerned. It was only the portion to the west and south of the present district of British Tippera that was converted into the Zamindari of Roshanabad.

This fact becomes more clear in Irfan Habib's *An Atlas of the Mughal Empire: Political and Economic Maps with detailed notes, bibliography and index* in which he mentions Tripura as Tipara.

Further, it is explained on Page No. 46 about the reference of 2 books namely (i) Yahia-bin-Sirhindi, *Tarikh-i-Mubarakshahi*, edited by M.H.Gohain, Biblico Indico, Calcutta (1931) and (2) Anandram Mukhlis, *Safarnama-i-Mukhalis*, edited by Saiyyed Azhar Ali, Rampur (1946). As per these references, Mukhiis made his journey in 1745 CE. The description about the territory given by medieval writers as well as the writers of the mid 18th century provide the following about the name and other neighbouring areas, "A large tract where the Tipperah held sway it adjoined Bhati. The two statements occur in *Ain-i-Akbari* as the account of Tavernier (Tippara)". *Ain-i-Akbari* does not assert Mughal suzerainty over it but in *Iqbalnama* 'Tripura' is given as one of the three *Mahals* of Bengal that did not belong to any of its *Sircars*. A successful expedition against Tipara is described in *Baharistan-i-Ghaibi* (spells Tippera). The limits of the principality during 17th century was probably identical with those shown in Rennell's maps (spells Tiperah). It included the entire territory of Tripura (The older Tippera Hill tracts) and parts of the modern districts of Tippera. *Baharistan-i-Ghaibi* further informs Udaipur as the capital of Tippera, which signifies the integrity of Tripura. As per *Ain-i-Akbari*, "The next worthy king after Deva Manikya was Vijay Manikya, who was a contemporary of Akbar. He was an independent King of Tripura."²⁵

Thus, on the basis of above-mentioned facts we can say that Tripura remained independent state inspite of several Mughal inroads.

Economic Impact

After studying all the historical sites of the Mughal inroads in Tripura, we can say that during the reign of Yasodhar Manikya Tripura was under the occupation of the Mughals for about three years (1618CE – 1620CE). The invaders captured elephants and royal treasures. The Mughal army marauded and

looted the wealth of the subjects.²⁶ Thus, the wealth of Tripura flowed to the Mughal side and this small state faced a lot of economic problems.

During the reign of Kalyan Manikya (1628CE-1660CE) Tripura was invaded by the Bengal Subadar Shah Shuja, but no significant success was achieved even after labouring for one year. The district of Mirzafur was made the frontier of the Imperial dominion.²⁷

It is interesting to note that in the revenue records of Bengal Suba revised at the time of Shah Shuja in 1658CE, Sarkar Udaipur was recorded as a revenue paying centre.²⁸ The mention of Sarkar Udaipur in all his land-grants is indicative of the Mughal allegiance, real or nominal, particularly for the western plains and thus beading Tripura full of economic problems.

Religious Impact

The Mughal inroads in Tripura led to religious tensions in Tripura. We know that the Mughals followed Islam, which is against of idol worship. When Emperor Jahangir was in power at Delhi; at that time Bengal was in the command of Ibrahim Khan Fatejang and Mirza Nurulla Khan. Both these Governors of Bengal attacked Tripura and arrested its ruler Yasodhar Manikya and they prohibited the worship of Chaudda Devata and the Tripureswari Kali. They built a mosque at Udaipur and encouraged the Mullas, Pirs and Fakirs to convert some Hindus to Islam.²⁹

Cultural Impact

Culture plays an important role in society. The Mughal inroads in Tripura had great cultural impact. Two different religions, Hinduism and Islam in addition to Buddhist tradition laid the formula of cultural synthesis in Tripura. Now, Tripura witnessed the emergence of a secular identity as the people of different religions walked together to form a common cultural identity of Tripura.

5. Social Impact

Man lives in the society. Social life forms the best platform for communal harmony. Before the inroads of Mughals, the small state of Tripura formed peaceful co-existence of its people. But after the Mughal inroads in Tripura, the people of Tripura

knew the fact that self-help is the best help. So, they endeavoured to accept the latest means of a developed society. The people of this State had the feelings of oneness to retaliate the Mughal invaders. Many of them joined the military organization. Thus, it created a social mobilization among the people of Tripura.

6. Military Preparedness

After the Mughal inroads in Tripura, the military preparedness reached new heights. The preparation of the army presupposed various factors like the development of the means of warfare, human, animal and material sources. In an effect to modernize the army, Vijay Manikya (C.1532-1563 CE) started organizing the cavalry. He not only imported the horses, but also employed the Afghan soldiers³⁰ in the branch and thus introduced a new element in the Tripura army. Although, according to *Ain-i-Akbari*, the strength of Tripura cavalry was negligible.³¹

Conclusion

Thus, on the basis of above facts one can surely say that the Mughal inroads in Tripura were not automatic in nature but a result of constant endeavours from the Mughal Governors. Though, they became successful in their endeavours, but they could not annex the state of Tripura completely in the Mughal dominion. Except a small portion of its territory, the remaining part of Tripura never fell prey to the Mughals. The historical documents like *Ain-i-Akbari*, *Baharistan-i-Ghaibi* and *Sri Raj-mala* provide the authenticity of its independent status. If we critically analyse the Mughal inroads in Tripura, we do find that they played a significant role in propelling the state towards modernity. Of course, the Mughal inroads in Tripura proved to be a lesson for motivation, self-awareness and a challenging task for the people of Tripura.

Notes and References

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2. W. W. Hunter, 'A Statistical Account of Bengal' (London, 1876) Vol-VI P-463 (1973 reprint).
3. Comment by Dr. Dinesh Ch. Sarkar in the *Journal of Asiatic Society of Bengal*, Vol XVII, No.2 (1951), pp.76-77.

4. S. N. Guha Thakurta, *Tripura*, NBT, New Delhi, (1986), p.2.
5. *Ghazi-Nama*: It was written by Monohar Saikh. It was a life story of Shamsar Ghazi who started his Career as a vassal of the Tripura Kings and gradually usurped the political power. The exact date of writing the 'Ghazi-Nama' cannot be correctly ascertained. Monohar Saikh, the author was however, a devoted friend and a contemporary of Shamsar Ghazi. It may, therefore, be presumed that the 'Ghazi-Nama' was composed during the last half of the 18th century. It has also been confirmed by the findings of Dinesh Ch. Sen in his book—*Brihat Banga*, Vol-II (C.U.1342 BC, p.1041).
6. Vijoy Champak, *A Life Story of Champak Roy*, who was the uncle of Ratna Manikya. It was written by Saikha Mahaddi.
7. *Tripura Desar Kather Lekha*: It was written in 1724 CE. It was also known as *Tripura Buranji*. Two Assamese envoys namely Arjundas Bairagi and Ratna Kandali Sarma were sent by the Ahom King Rudre Singh on diplomatic missions to the court of Ratna Manikya II. The left this interesting account about Tripura.
8. *Krishnamala*: It is an account of the reign of Krishna Manikya.
9. S. K. Bhuyan, (ed.), *Tripura Buranji*, Government of Assam (1938), p.34: In Tripuri language the word 'Pha' means father. According to the versions of Ratna Kandali Sarma and Arjun Das Bairagi, the two envoys of the Ahom Kings to the court of Ratna Manikya, it appears that originally the rulers of Tripura did not assume the title of king; their names ended with the word 'Pha'.
10. Kalikaranjan Qanungo, *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Bengal*, Vol-XVI. No.2 (1950), p.216.
11. R. C. Majumder, *Bengal Desher Itihas*, Vol-II, (General Printers) & Publishers, Calcutta), p.488; Kali Prasanna Sen, *Rajmala*, Vol-I, pp.68-69.
12. It is now generally believed that the Manikya dynasty in Tripura began from the reign of Dharma Manikya or his predecessors Maha Manikya, and not from the reign of Ratna Manikya as was believed in the past on the basis of a wrong reading of the date of the coins issued during his time. Again, some historical evidence also suggests that the title 'Manikya' was found inscribed on a quarter rupee coin dated 1211CE of Vijay Manikya, the raja of Ganda, a bordering state of Tripura. One may, therefore, infer that the Tripura rulers adopted the title. Tripura District Gazetteers, *op.cit.*, pp.74-76.
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14. A. C. Bhattacharya, *Progressive Tripura*, Inter-India Publications, New Delhi, (1985), pp.16-17.

15. Debabrata Goswami, *Military History of Tripura (1490 to 1947)*, Tripura State Tribal Cultural research Institute & Museum, Agartala, p.20.
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17. *Ibid*, p.19
18. Palash Saha, (ed.), *Tripura 2010 Year Book*, p.54.
19. A. C. Bhattacharya, *Progressive Tripura* (1985) p.21.
20. *Ibid*, p.23.
21. Palash Saha, (ed), 'Tripura 2010 Year Book', pp.52-33 and J Gan Chaudheri, *A Political History of Tripura* (1985), Inter-India Publications, New Delhi, p.27.
22. Maharaj Kumar Sahadev Bikram Kishore, *Tripura Historical Documents* (1994), Bhartiya Itihas Sankalan Samiti, Agartala, pp.1-2.
23. A. C. Bhattacharya, *Progressive Tripura, op.cit.*, p.25.
24. Stewart, *History of Bengal*, p.267. and A. C. Bhattacharya, *Progressive Tripura, op.cit.*, pp.18-19.
25. Abul Fazl, *Ain-i-Akbari Vo-II*, Translated vs edited by Jerret H.S., Calcutta (1942), p.130.
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27. Azad-Al-Husaini, *Naubahar-i-Murshid Culi Khani*, translated by Sarkar J. N. in *Bengal: Past and Present*, Vol-LSIX, Serial-132, Calcutta, 1950, p.1.
28. Sing K.C, 'Rajmale', 1896, Comilla, p.84.
29. J. Gan Chaudhari, *A Political History of Tripura, op.cit.*, p.27-28.
30. Sen, Kaliprasanna, *Sri Rajmala* (in Bengali), Vol-III, Agartala, (1927), p.190.
31. Debabrata Goswami, *Military History of Tripura, op.cit.*, p.51.